

Chemomechanical Caries Removal agents: a craze in the market

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Abstract - Dental caries, a disease that affects people worldwide, is typically treated using the traditional method involving dental burs. However, this approach has many disadvantages, such as the noise of the machine, which makes patients uncomfortable, and the unpleasant sensation of drilling the tooth structure. These issues can be especially challenging in patients who are children, fearful or uncooperative. Recently, the demand for dentistry has shifted towards minimal caries excavation techniques, including chemomechanical caries removal (CMCR) and various agents. CMCR works by softening infected dentine, which is then gently removed using specific agents, either synthetic or natural. This review will explore different systems of CMCR agents in detail.

Keywords: *Minimal intervention dentistry (MID), Chemo-Mechanical Caries Removal (CMCR), Covid -19, Carisolv, Papacaries, Carie- carie, BRIX 3000*

I. INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent worldwide disease remains dental caries as a public health challenge among the younger generation. Dental caries is a localized dissolution and destruction of the calcified tooth tissues. Caries removal with conventional drill method is associated with several disadvantages like (i) patient perception that drilling is unpleasant, (ii) use of local anaesthesia frequently, (iii) thermal effect deleteriously due to drilling, (iv) pressure effect on pulp and (v) excessive removal sound tooth. This factor leads to rejection of dental treatment by the children and their parents because of fear and anxiety. [1] Advancement in operative dentistry for management of dental caries has evolved from G.V.Black's "Extension for prevention" to "construction with conservation".[2]

In today scenario minimal invasive dentistry adopted a philosophy that integrates prevention, remineralization and minimal intervention for the replacement and placement of restoration. It has reached the objective of using least invasive surgical approach with minimal removal of healthy tissues which includes following different techniques like:

1. Air abrasion
2. Atraumatic restorative technique
3. Sono abrasion
4. Laser
5. Chemomechanical caries removal (CMCR)

Among all the technique, CMCR holds a promise as an effective alternative to traditional method for removal of caries. As a name suggests, it involves application of chemical solution to the infected dental tissue followed by gentle removal by hand, preserving the healthy structure and then restore it by Glass ionomer cement (GIC) or Composite resin that bond with dentin surface. It has multiple advantages such as: more comfortable and less pain perception, less anxiety and discomfort, dental tissue preservation, no pulpal irritation, better caries removal in uncooperative children and physically handicapped patients. According to the data available, it has been used as an alternative non aerosol technique during the period of corona virus disease in 2019 (covid-19).[3-4]

Since 1975, various chemical composition has been introduced for CMCR agents which can be classified into sodium hypochlorite (GK 101, Caridex and Carisolv) and enzyme based (Papacarie, Biosolv, Carie-Care, BRIX-3000). Although sodium based agent have found to be effective but each product have certain drawbacks so these were removed from the market but some are changed to update. The present review aim to address current market trending chemomechanical caries removal agent in details.[5]

A. Carisolv

In 1998, Mediteam in Sweden developed Carisolv which was in the form of a pink gel with special designed hand instrument that can be applied in caries lesion. It is marketed in two syringes, one containing sodium hypochlorite solution and other a pink viscous gel which contain amino acid like lysine, leucine and glutamic acid together with carboxymethyl cellulose to make it viscous and erythrocin dye to make it visible in use. As it is a gel, the volume required is 1 ml. The advantage is, it neither requires heating nor a delivery system. [6-7] After 2004, modified gel was introduced, where colouring agent was removed and amino acid concentration was reduced by half and sodium hypochlorite concentration was increased.

New Carisolv system in 2013 was introduced by Rubicon Life Science, where they incorporated of minimal invasive burs (Cera and polymer burs) and special Carisolv detector dye to shorten the caries excavation time. This new system provides an excellent bonding surface for bonded restoration. Despite its effectiveness, Carisolv was not a runaway success mainly because it required (i)extensive training and registration of professionals (ii) customised instrument which increase the cost of the solution that resulted few people to access Carisolv solution.[6] (Fig. 1)

Fig.1 Ganesh M, Parikh D. Chemomechanical caries removal (CMCR) agents: Review and clinical application in primary teeth. J Dent Oral Hyg. 2011 Mar 31;3(3):34-45.¹¹

B. Papacarie

Bussadori et al. in 2003, by formula & Acao, brazil manufacture introduced Papacarie gel. Papacarie is a Portuguese word meaning “caries eater”. It consists of papin enzymes chloramine, toluidine blue, salts, preservatives, a thickener, deionized water and stabilizer. It is a gel syringe that have 3 ml of solution. The main action is due to the presence of the enzyme of papin which has a proteolytic, bactericidal and anti-inflammatory actions.[8] The manufacturer recommends using the blunt spoon excavator however, good results have been reported by using the No.4 Carisolv hand instrument. It has proved to be highly effective and maximum preservation of healthy tooth tissue but as an enzymatic CMCR product it is considered to be an expensive procedure. [9] (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 Ganesh M, Parikh D. Chemomechanical caries removal (CMCR) agents: Review and clinical application in primary teeth. J Dent Oral Hyg. 2011 Mar 31;3(3):34-45.¹¹

C. Carie-care

Carie-care was introduced in 2010, manufactured by Uni-biotech Pharmaceutical Pvt.Ltd, Chennai, India, in collaboration with Vittal Mallya Scientific Research Foundation.[6] The main components are papin, chloramine and dye. It also contains essential oil from plants, such as clove oil, which gives mild anaesthetic and anti-inflammatory effects. the preparation has a gelling agent in accurate percentage to give exact consistency that prevents the gel to be spill over and being applied. The intention of presenting a new agent that can cost lesser than Papacarie and can be easily available.[8] (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3 Puri A, Gaurav K, Kaur J, Sethi D, Jindal L, Jain S. Chemomechanical Caries Removal: An Overview. *IDA Lud J-le Dent.* 2020;4(2):27-38.²

D. BRIX 3000

BRIX 3000 is the recent CMCR agent introduced in 2012 by BRIX Medical science, Argentina. The exception of this product is the amount of papain used i.e 10 % to 3000 U/mg and the Encapsulated Buffer Emulsion technology, which gives the gel the ideal pH to immobilize the enzyme and liberate them at the moment of exerting its proteolysis on the collagen. It did not contain chloramines than enhance its toxicological safety features.[3] (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4 Felizardo KR, de Alvarenga Barradas NP, Guedes GF, Ferreira FD, Lopes MB. Use of Brix-3000 Enzymatic gel in mechanical chemical removal of caries: Clinical Case Report. *Journal of Health Sciences.* 2018 Jun 30;20(2):87-93.¹⁰

II. CONCLUSION

Chemomechanical caries removal agents provide significant features for clinician to opt for routine practice as a painless and non-invasive approach ensuring a positive patient-dentist relationship with very fearful and anxious patients, old patients, children as well as special healthcare needs. CMCR also holds up promising solution in the era of covid-19 pandemic as the risk for transmission of respiratory infection is less which eliminates the use of high speed hand-piece in excavating dental caries. However, further studies are recommended to obtain more clinical evidence for regular use of this method in clinical practice.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bussadori SK, Castro LC, Galvão AC. Papain gel: a new chemo-mechanical caries removal agent. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry.* 2005 Jan 1;30(2):115.
- [2] Puri A, Gaurav K, Kaur J, Sethi D, Jindal L, Jain S. Chemomechanical Caries Removal: An Overview. *IDA Lud J-le Dent.* 2020;4(2):27-38.
- [3] Abdelaziz E, Badran A, Allam G. Chemomechanical Caries Removal Agents and Their Applications in Pediatric Dentistry. *Advanced Dental Journal.* 2022 Jan 1;4(1):11-8.
- [4] Shrimahalakshmi CN, Rajasekaran S. Awareness and Clinical Application of Chemo Mechanical Caries Removal Agent among General Dentists and Dental Specialists in the Era Of Covid-19 Pandemic: A Questionnaire Survey. *Int J Dentistry Oral Sci.* 2021 Sep 4;8(9):4284-91.
- [5] Souza TF, Martins ML, Magno MB, Vicente-Gomila JM, Fonseca-Gonçalves A, Maia LC. Worldwide research trends on the use of chemical–mechanical caries removal products over the years: a critical review. *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry.* 2022 Jul 13:1-5.
- [6] Mithra NH, Abhishek M. Chemomechanical caries removal: a conservative and pain-free approach. *Adv Res Gastroentero Hepatol.* 2017;5(3):69-71.
- [7] Chakravorty S, Nair VV, Kumar S, Chopra K, Salyankar MS, Kumar SD. Chemomechanical Caries Removal: An Update. *Journal of Advanced Medical and Dental Sciences Research.* 2022;10(1):8-13.
- [8] Mazumdar P, Choudhury SR, Das D, Murmu LB. Chemomechanical Caries Removal Agents-An Overview. *Res Gate.* 2019;35(1):9-14.
- [9] Hamama HH, Yiu C, Burrow M. Current update of chemomechanical caries removal methods. *Australian dental journal.* 2014 Dec;59(4):446-56.
- [10] Felizardo KR, de Alvarenga Barradas NP, Guedes GF, Ferreira FD, Lopes MB. Use of Brix-3000 Enzymatic gel in mechanical chemical removal of caries: Clinical Case Report. *Journal of Health Sciences.* 2018 Jun 30;20(2):87-93.